

EFFECT OF SURFACE TREATMENT AND WEAVE STRUCTURE ON MODE I INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE BEHAVIOR OF GLASS WOVEN FABRIC COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness tests were carried out by using double cantilever beam (DCB) specimens with plain glass woven fabric composites. DCB specimens were cut parallel to both weft and warp directions of woven fabrics. Five types of surface treatment were performed on the glass woven fabrics. Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness of weft tested specimens were higher compared to warp tested specimens in the case of all types of surface treatment. Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness decreased with increasing concentration of silane coupling agent. Methanol solvent washing caused decrease of fracture toughness. It could be concluded on the basis of the fracture surface observation that mode I interlaminar fracture toughness was correlated to the crack path with changing surface treatment.

1. INTRODUCTION

Proper design of the interface between fiber and matrix is necessary for tailoring the mechanical properties of composite materials. Many investigation for interfacial properties of composite materials have been presented[1-6]. There are a lot of different viewpoints to the interface in these investigations according to each researcher. Some evaluation methods of the interface, for example the method by embedded-single-filament tensile test[7,8], pull-out test[9,10] and microbond test[11,12], have been carried out to try to identify the interfacial properties of composites.

One of our targets to design the interface is to identify the influences of the interfacial properties on crack growth behavior of composite materials. Authors presented previously that mode I interlaminar fracture toughness of plain glass woven fabric composites were significantly affected by kinds and concentration of silane coupling agents[13,14]. In the previous work the mechanism for the effects of surface treatment on fracture toughness has not been so cleared, because the weave structure also might affect on the fracture toughness. In this work to clarify the effects of both interfacial properties and weave structure have been actually carried out on mode I crack growth behavior of the plain glass woven fabric composites with different surface treatment. The mechanism for the effects of surface treatment on mode I interlaminar fracture toughness of the woven fabric composites has been discussed by fracture surface observations using scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

2. EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

2-1 Materials

Materials used in this investigation were plain glass fabrics of 44(warp)x34(weft) strands count over inch (WE18W: Nitto Boseki Company) as reinforcement. The fiber strands from the E-glass fiber fabric consisted of 400 glass fiber filaments of 9 μ m diameter. Surface treatment was performed on glass fiber fabrics by changing concentration of γ -methacryloxy-

propyltrimethoxysilane (A174: Nippon Unicar Company) as called methacryl silane. The concentration of methacryl silane was 0.01wt%, 0.4wt% and 1.0wt%. Moreover glass fiber fabrics were washed with methanol solvent after finishing the 0.4wt% methacryl silane. 0.4wt% γ -glycidoxypropyl-trimethoxysilane (A-187: Nippon Unicar Company) as called epoxy silane was also used as surface treatment agent. There are five surface treatment conditions totally as shown in Table 1. Vinylester resin (Ripoxy R806) of unsaturated polyester as matrix was polymerized with 0.7wt% methyl-ethyl-ketone-peroxide. Twenty plies plain glass woven fabric composite laminates were fabricated by hand lay-up technique. The laminates for mode I fracture toughness tests were 4mm thick.

2-2 Fracture Toughness Test

Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness tests were carried out using double cantilever beam (DCB) specimens which were cut out parallel to both the weft and warp fiber directions. The DCB specimen and set apparatus used in this work are shown in Fig.1. Initial defects for the DCB specimens were introduced into the specimens by inserting 40 μ m PTFE film during molding the laminates. The fracture toughness tests were carried out by using Instron 4206 machine under stroke control of 1mm/min. The crack propagation length was measured on one side of the specimen with traveling microscope at a magnification of x100. Displacement of the testing machine was used as the crack opening displacement (COD) on the load line. Fracture toughness value was calculated according to JIS K7086.

3. RESULTS

3-1 Effect of Surface Treatment on Fracture Toughness

Relation between mode I fracture toughness and crack extension, R-curves, of five types of specimens with different surface treatment showed different tendencies in weft directions. Two kinds of crack growth patterns, stable and unstable crack growth, were observed during DCB tests. For the stable crack growth the crack traveled slowly and controllably across the laminates, whereas for the unstable crack growth the crack traveled uncontrollably across the laminates at a fast speed.

Figure 2 shows R-curves for weft tested specimens. 0.01wt% methacryl silane finished specimen displayed almost constant fracture toughness with increase of crack extension after about 10mm crack extension ($\Delta a=10$ mm). On the other hand in the cases of 0.4wt% and 1.0wt% methacryl silane finished specimen there were some points in R-curves which fracture toughness rapidly decreased, and the R-curves displayed saw teeth like behavior. The unstable fracture occurred at these points where fracture toughness started to decrease rapidly. The crack growth behavior changed from stable pattern to unstable pattern with increase of concentration in methacryl silane. R-curve for methanol washed specimen presented also saw teeth like behavior. In the case of 0.4wt% epoxy silane finished specimen, the fracture toughness was remained constant with increasing crack extension.

Initial values of mode I interlaminar fracture toughness which was calculated from the point of onset of nonlinearity(PNL), 5% offset point(P₅) and maximum load point(P_{Max}) in the initial load-displacement curves. The initial values of mode I interlaminar fracture toughness for weft tested specimens calculated from these load points were summarized in Table 2. When P₅ point appeared after P_{Max} point, the fracture toughness in P₅ point was calculated from P_{Max} point. The fracture toughness in PNL and P₅ points presented the highest value in the case of 0.4wt% methacryl silane. On the other hand the fracture toughness in P_{Max} point for methacryl silane finished specimens decreased with increasing concentration. In addition, methanol washed specimen displayed lower fracture toughness than 0.4wt% methacryl silane finished specimen in the three cases. Also the fracture toughness for 0.4wt% methacryl silane finished specimen was higher compared to 0.4wt% epoxy silane finished specimen in the three cases.

Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness values at $\Delta a=20$ mm were calculated as propagation values of fracture toughness. In the case of the saw teeth like R-curve such as 1.0wt% methacryl silane finished specimen, the propagation value was calculated from top two points

around $\Delta a=20\text{mm}$ such as points A and B as shown Fig.2(c), which were initiation points of unstable fracture. Relation between the propagation values of mode I fracture toughness for weft tested specimens and concentration of silane coupling agents are shown in Fig.3. The propagation values for methacryl silane finished specimens decreased with increase of concentration in methacryl silane. Methanol washing caused decrease of the propagation value of fracture toughness. 0.4wt% epoxy silane finished specimen displayed almost same propagation value as 0.4wt% methacryl silane finished specimen.

3-3 Effect of Weave Structure on Fracture Toughness

The initial values of fracture toughness for warp tested specimens calculated respectively from PNL, P₅ and P_{max} points were summarized in Table 3. Compared these fracture toughness with weft tested specimens (Table 2), in almost of all cases the fracture toughness for weft tested specimens were higher than that for warp tested specimens.

The propagation values for both weft and warp tested specimens are shown in Fig.4. The propagation values for the weft tested specimens was higher compared to the warp tested specimens in all types of surface treatment, because weave density between weft and warp fiber is different. Weave structure affected greatly on fracture toughness for the woven fabric composites.

3-3 Fracture Surface Observation

Figure 5 shows SEM micrographs of the mode I fracture surface around $\Delta a=20\text{mm}$ for weft tested specimens. In the case of 0.01wt% methacryl silane finished specimen, the fiber strands were exposed on the fracture surface. On the other hand in the case of 0.4wt% and 1.0wt% methacryl silane finished specimens the fracture surface was covered with matrix resin. This difference between them may be correlated to the crack path. In 0.01wt% methacryl silane finished specimen the crack path run into the interface region around fiber strands, and in 0.4wt% and 1.0wt% methacryl silane finished specimens the crack traveled through resin region between plies. In methanol washed specimen the fracture surface was covered with resin and in epoxy silane finished specimen fiber strands were exposed on the fracture surface. That means the crack path run through resin rich region in methanol washed specimen and interface region in epoxy silane finished specimen, respectively.

4. DISCUSSION

It was cleared that mode I interlaminar fracture toughness for the woven fabric composites depended on surface treatment. Actually, surface treatment affected on the crack path and consequently the different crack path changed the fracture toughness.

Chou et.al. discussed effect of fiber orientation on mode I fracture toughness of CFRP laminates[15]. According to this investigation, in the case of transverse direction of fiber to the crack growth direction mode I interlaminar fracture toughness was higher compared to any other directions. Hence, mode I fracture toughness of woven fabric composites may be significantly affected by transverse fiber to the crack growth direction. The number of the transverse fiber strands whose are in weft fiber direction is larger compared to warp fiber direction. So that the weft tested specimens displayed higher fracture toughness compared to warp tested specimens. The difference of fracture toughness between weft and warp tested specimens may be due to the difference in amount of increase derived from the transverse fiber strands.

The crack propagating area on the transverse fiber was identified in all types of surface treatment conditions by observations of mode I fracture surface. Crack growth region under mode I loading for the plain glass woven fabric composites changed with varying conditions of surface treatment. In the case of methacryl silane finished specimens the crack growth region changed from interface region to resin rich region between plies with increasing concentration of methacryl silane. Then amount of the region which the crack propagated on the transverse fibers changed. That means the amount of increase derived from the transverse fiber strands changed with varying conditions of surface treatment. For example compared 0.01wt% with 1.0wt% methacryl silane finished specimens, the crack propagating area on a transverse fiber

strand for 0.01wt% was larger than that for 1.0wt% as shown in Fig.6. Then, the amount of increase in fracture toughness derived from the transverse fiber strand for 0.1wt% was higher compared to 1.0wt%. That is why fracture toughness for 0.01wt% was higher compared to 1.0wt%. Hence it can be noted that the crack propagating area depend on surface treatment conditions and the fracture toughness for woven fabric composites is affected by the crack propagating area on the transverse fiber strand.

5. SUMMARY

Mode I interlaminar fracture behavior depend on both weave structure and surface treatment. Mode I interlaminar crack growth behavior for woven fabric composites changed from the unstable manner to the stable manner with varying surface treatment conditions. The weft tested specimens which have more transverse fiber strands to crack growth direction displayed higher fracture toughness compared to the warp tested specimens regardless of surface treatment. The crack propagating area depend on surface treatment, and then mode I fracture toughness is affected by the crack propagating area.

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Table 1 Surface treatment conditions

Silane Coupling Agent	Concentration (wt%)	Methanol Washing
Methacryl Silane	0.01	×
	0.4	×
	1.0	×
	0.4	○
Epoxy Silane	0.4	×

Fig.1 DCB specimen with loading apparatus.

Fig.2 Relation between fracture toughness and crack extension of weft tested specimens for plain glass woven fabric composites; (a) 0.01wt% methacryl silane, (b) 0.4wt% methacryl silane, (c) 1.0wt% methacryl silane, (d) methanol washed 0.4wt% methacryl silane and (e) 0.4wt% epoxy silane.

Table 2 Initial values of mode I fracture toughness for weft tested specimens of plain woven fabric composites.

Type	GIC (kN/m)		
	PNL	P5	PMax
methacryl silane 0.01wt%	0.27	0.37	0.59
methacryl silane 0.4wt%	0.30	0.40	0.44
methacryl silane 1.0wt%	0.12	0.15	0.22
methacryl silane 0.4wt%/methanol	0.23	0.29	0.36
epoxy silane 0.4wt%	0.18	→	0.23

Fig.3 Relation between mode I interlaminar fracture toughness at $\Delta a=20\text{mm}$ and concentration of silane coupling agents.

Table 3 Initial values of mode I fracture toughness for warp tested specimens of plain woven fabric composites.

Type	GIC (kN/m)		
	PNL	P5	PMax
methacryl silane 0.01wt%	0.10	0.15	0.39
methacryl silane 0.4wt%	0.21	0.25	0.34
methacryl silane 1.0wt%	0.18	→	0.18
methacryl silane 0.4wt%/methanol	0.18	0.25	0.37
epoxy silane 0.4wt%	0.18	→	0.21

Fig.4 Comparison of mode I fracture toughness at $\Delta a=20\text{mm}$ between weft and warp tested specimens for plain glass woven fabric composites.

Fig.5 SEM micrographs of mode I fracture surface for weft tested specimens of plain glass woven fabric composites; (a) 0.01wt% methacryl silane, (b) 0.4wt% methacryl silane, (c) 1.0wt% methacryl silane, (d) methanol washed 0.4wt% methacryl silane and (e) 0.4wt% epoxy silane.

Fig.6 Schematic diagram of crack path on a transverse fiber strand to the crack propagating direction in the case of 0.01wt% and 1.0wt% methacryl silane finished specimens.